

ADDITIVE FABRICATION OF HYDROXYAPATITE CERAMICS USING MILLIMETER-WAVE AND SUB-TERAHERTZ RADIATION

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Additive manufacturing of ceramic products is a challenging task in today's materials science and technology. Two basically different approaches are being pursued in the implementation of this task: (1) additive production of a green ceramic part followed by sintering, and (2) localized sintering of a powder composition by a concentrated energy flow according to a 3D model of the final product. This paper reports recent results on the use of millimeter-wave and sub-terahertz electromagnetic radiation in the implementation of additive fabrication methods of ceramic products.

The material under study was hydroxyapatite, $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, which is a promising candidate for biomedical applications. The experiments were carried out with the hydroxyapatite powder GAP-85d (Polistom, Russia). The particle size of the powder was 0.7 – 2 μm , and the specific surface area was 3 – 10 m^2/g . The powder compositions for the experiments on layer-by-layer millimeter-wave sintering were prepared by colloidal processing. It was found that the optimal concentration of the dispersed phase of hydroxyapatite in an aqueous solution, required for the deposition of sufficiently dense, fracture-free homogeneous layers, was close to 35 wt. %. About 1 wt. % of surfactant (ammonium polyacrylate) was added to the suspension to improve the stability against aggregation. Sintered hydroxyapatite disks with a diameter of 8 mm and a density of 70% of the theoretical density were used as scaffolds. The disperse hydroxyapatite suspension layers were applied to the scaffolds by the doctor blade method. The thickness of each applied layer was 0.1 - 0.15 mm.

The millimeter-wave sintering was carried out in the workchamber of the gyrotron system for high-temperature millimeter-wave processing of materials operating at a frequency of 24 GHz with a maximum output power of 5 kW [1]. For improved uniformity of the temperature distribution within the heated body, the sample was placed in a cylindrical zirconia crucible which was built into the heat-insulating container made of a highly porous alumina-based material. The sample temperature was measured using a B-type thermocouple brought in direct contact with the powder layer. The accuracy of temperature measurements was no worse than ± 5 °C in the temperature range 1000 – 1450 °C.

The sintering process was carried out at a residual air pressure of about 1 Pa. At the initial stage, the sample was heated to 800 °C at a relatively slow rate of 10 °C/min in order to remove the surfactant and water vapor adsorbed on the particles of the powder material. Then the heating rate was increased to 20 °C/min, and the sample was heated to a temperature of 1150 °C with no isothermal hold. The millimeter-wave power required for heating did not exceed 400 W. To create a multi-layer sample, application of a hydroxyapatite suspension layer and the sintering procedure was repeated. A more detailed description of the experimental procedure can be found elsewhere [2].

Shown in Fig. 1 (a) is a SEM image of an obtained 5-layer sample. It can be seen that the layers are parallel and uniform. At higher magnification (Fig. 1 (b)) it can be seen that there is a significant remaining porosity in the sintered layers, and at some portions of the boundary between layers there are chains of pores. It should be noted that it was not intended to sinter the material to full density, and the processes were performed without the isothermal stage of sintering. The porosity remaining in the periphery of the sample is beneficial for some biomedical applications since it facilitates penetration of natural tissues into the biocompatible ceramic implant.

At the fractured surface of the sample there is a layered structure, visible due to the density gradient within each layer. It occurs that during the application of the hydroxyapatite suspension, too intense absorption of moisture occurs in the porous substrate. The hydroxyapatite particles do not have time to reorganize and form an agglomerated coral-like structure with significant porosity. The packing density of the particles in each layer increases with increasing distance from the substrate because the absorption of water slows down. This structure is inherited in microwave sintering. This results in a high density, in excess of 90%, at the top of each layer and a low density of about 70% in the areas adjacent to the previous layer. The pore size is determined by the granulometric composition of the powder, and in the described case it is a few microns. However, in the volume of the layers large pores, of the order of tens of microns in size, are also found, originating from an entrainment of air into the suspension during mixing and application. Therefore, in order to improve the uniformity of the layers and regulate the porous structure it is necessary to optimize the rheology of the suspension and to adjust the absorbing properties of the substrate by changing the pre-sintering temperature and/or moistening the substrate to a certain level.

The microhardness measurements accomplished on the samples have yielded the values of 3.1 – 3.4 GPa in the sintered scaffold and 0.3 – 0.4 GPa inside the individual layers. No delamination of the layered structure was observed after indentation.

Fig. 1. SEM images of a fractured surface of a multi-layer hydroxyapatite sample obtained by repeated layer-by-layer millimeter-wave sintering (a) and a magnified image of a boundary between two of the layers (b).

A separate series of experiments was undertaken to demonstrate feasibility of heating by sub-terahertz radiation beams to achieve ultra-rapid, strongly localized consolidation of hydroxyapatite powder [3]. In these experiments, electromagnetic radiation from a sub-terahertz gyrotron operating at a frequency of 263 GHz with a maximum power of 1 kW was focused into a spot with a size of about 2.5 mm using a purposely designed radiation

transmission line [4]. The hydroxyapatite powder was placed in a rectangular crucible made of porous alumina to form a powder layer with a length of 57 mm, a width of 12 mm and a thickness of 2.5 mm. The crucible with the powder was positioned under the sub-terahertz radiation beam at such a level that the focal point was slightly beneath the surface of the powder layer. Upon turning the gyrotron power on, the crucible was held still for about 5 s to provide initial heating of the powder at the starting point. Then the crucible was displaced relative to the beam at a velocity of about 0.5 mm/s, which was adjusted continuously so that uniform glowing of the heated powder could be observed. The gyrotron output power required to implement this heating regime was found to be about 100 W, which provided a radiation intensity of about 2 kW/cm² in the focal spot. As a result of processing, localized consolidation has been achieved in a strip with a width of 3–5 mm over the entire depth of the powder layer. These first experimental results indicate that the use of focused beams of millimeter-wave / sub-terahertz radiation can be a promising approach in developing additive methods of ceramic products fabrication based on localized consolidation.

In a similar manner, lower-frequency millimeter-wave radiation can be used for the same purpose, with a corresponding increase of the focal spot size. Densification of a layer of hydroxyapatite powder under localized heating by a Gaussian beam of 24 GHz millimeter-wave radiation was simulated within a quasi-3D model: a two-dimensional heat transfer equation with respect to transversal coordinates was complemented by heat removal conditions on the top and bottom surfaces of the layer. The heat removal was via thermal radiation which corresponds to the processing in vacuum. The absorbed microwave power was calculated at each time step using the experimentally obtained temperature dependencies of the complex dielectric permittivity of hydroxyapatite [5]. The dependency of the complex dielectric permittivity on density was accounted for using the effective medium approximation. The dependency of thermal conductivity of hydroxyapatite on temperature and density was taken into account in a similar manner using the data from [6]. The evolution of density during sintering was simulated using the master sintering curve approach [7]. The master sintering curve was constructed using the optical dilatometry data obtained in purposely designed millimeter-wave sintering experiments carried out at constant heating rates. The change in density was calculated at each time step of the simulation after computing the temperature distribution, assuming that the material is supplied to the zone of intense densification from the surrounding regions. The stresses associated with that were neglected.

Shown in Fig. 2 are the simulation results for the case when a 24 GHz Gaussian millimeter-wave beam with an effective radius of 1.8 cm moves at a velocity of 1 mm/s along a compacted hydroxyapatite workpiece with an initial relative density of about 0.54. The millimeter-wave power was chosen at such a level that an almost full density of the sintered material was achieved at the beam axis. The total radiation power absorbed in the workpiece in the steady state was about 945 W in this example. It can be seen from a comparison of Figs. 2a and 2b that the width of the region in which a high density of the sintered material is achieved is significantly less than the characteristic width of the temperature distribution, and even less than the effective width of the Gaussian beam.

Fig. 2. Distributions of temperature (a) and relative density (b) over a layer of hydroxyapatite powder heated by a focused Gaussian radiation beam with an effective radius of 1.8 cm, starting at ($x = 5$ cm, $y = 5$ cm) and moving along the x direction at a velocity of 1 mm/s, at the moment when the beam center arrives at ($x = 25$ cm, $y = 5$ cm).

In conclusion, this work demonstrates the potential of utilizing millimeter-wave and sub-terahertz radiation in the development of additive fabrication methods of ceramic products. The concentration of the radiation energy in the radiation beam is determined by the power of the radiation source and the electromagnetic wavelength, varying from 1.5 to 25 kW/cm² in the frequency range 24 – 263 GHz. In particular, this makes it possible to develop applications aimed on creating ceramic products with graded porous structures of different scale for enhanced biocompatibility.

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